

PLASTICITY OF POLYMERIC MATRICES AND
FAILURE MECHANISMS OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Plastic deformations have been shown to be typical of the majority of polymeric binders in thin interlayers. The effect of polymer matrix plastic deformations on strength properties of polymeric films and composite materials (fibre reinforced and filled with dispersed particles) has been investigated.

INTRODUCTION

Plastic deformation is known to have great effect on the type of failure and strength properties of plastic as well as qua si-brittle materials, e.g. polymers, metals and composites [1]. This article analyses the effect of plastic deformation on failure mechanisms in polymers, fibre reinforced and dispersion-filled composite materials.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When an external load is applied to a polymer sample having a man-made notch on it, a plastic deformation zone is formed in areas adjacent to the notch. It can be seen in both the plastic linear polymers and hypercrosslinked epoxy resins [2]. The form of the plastic zone depends on geometric sizes

of the notch and the sample itself, as well as on the load applied and properties of material.

According to the Dagdale-Barenblatt's model [3], in fine polymeric films the plasticity zone has the form of a thin strip stretched out perpendicular to the axis of the load applied.

In polymer sheets of finite thickness, the width of the plasticity zone along the axis of the load applied turns out to be finite. Experiments show [2] that in many materials it is equal to the sheet thickness. This is understandable if one remembers that the material yielding occurs along two shear lines that are at 45° to the direction of the load applied. Many experimental studies show the Dagdale-Barenblatt's equation to describe the length of the plasticity zone at the moment when the crack growth begins. However, it is the width of the plasticity zone that is of great importance for defining a criterion for the beginning of the crack growth [2].

If we assume [4] the crack growth to begin when the critical elongation of the material in the zone is reached, knowing the zone width (film thickness) and, due to Dagdale-Barenblatt, the displacement of the crack edges (δ) we can write the condition for the crack growth to begin, provided $e_0 = \delta^*/d$:

$$\delta^* \approx \sqrt{e_0 E \tau_0 d / C}, \quad (1)$$

where τ_0 is the matrix yield point;

E is the elasticity modulus of material;

d is the plastic zone width;

e_0 is the fracture elongation of material;

C is the notch length;

δ^* is the displacement of the crack edges.

Eq.(1) is equivalent to the Griffith energy criterion if we assume the effective fracture surface energy to be equal to the work of plastic deformation of material in the plastic zone:

$$\gamma_e = e_0 \tau_0 d \quad (2)$$

It is worth mentioning that the failure energy that characterizes the material brittleness depends on the sample thickness. Let us point out here that the work spent on plastic deformation of material before the crack tip exceeds the atomic bond breaking energy by a factor of 10^3-10^5 [5]. As shown in Fig.1, the failure energy and mechanical characteristics related to it (failure viscosity K_{1c} and critical crack edges displacement) are not the material constants.

Fig.1. Effective surface failure energy versus film thickness for polyethylene terephthalate (1), polyarylate (2) and ethylcellulose (3).

The plasticity zone width is equal to the film thickness only when no significant deformation strengthening of material takes place. Otherwise (as is the case with linear polymers) the zone width can be much greater than the sample thickness. For example, in polystyrene and polyvinylchloride, where the film thickness is 20 and 200 μm , the zone width is 350 and 440 μm , respectively [6]. In polyacrylate the plasticity zone width is equal to the film thickness at the moment when the crack growth begins, but later on, as the load increases, the crack growth is stabilized.

We have not yet arrived at complete understanding of either the effect of deformation strengthening, viscosity and

other properties of polymers or changes in the thickness, i.e. the effect of the stressed state on failure mechanism and parameters related to it (energy and viscosity of failure, critical displacement of crack edges). There is no quantitative theory at present and the qualitative understanding is far from perfect. Here, some important factors must be highlighted: 1) great reduction in the film thickness results in lower effective fracture surface energy, i.e. the crack propagates easily and failure becomes more brittle in nature; 2) linear polymeric matrix, which obtain deformation strengthening, may be much superior to the ones without deformation strengthening as far as the crack growth resistance is concerned; 3) as a result of restricted growth of plastic deformation the polymer failure energy goes down very abruptly (as compared to metals) when the sample thickness is increased.

Fig.2. Composite model: 1 - fibers, 2 - matrix, 3 - plastic zone in matrix.

Local plasticity of the matrix is also seen in reinforced plastics. With cracks going perpendicular to the direction of the fibres and tensile load applied along the fibers, a plastic deformation zone is formed in the matrix along the reinforcement axis (Fig.2). It must be pointed out that the plastic zone length can be compared to and even exceed the crack length "C" and that the zone length "y" is proportional to

"C". As a result, the failure energy increases with the growth of the crack length and the Griffith criterion cannot be used to describe the effect of defects on the strength of composites. It was shown [7,8] that dependence of strength of glass and organic fibre reinforced plastics on the crack length can be described by logarithmic (Fig.3) or power functions (3) and (4):

$$\sigma/\sigma_0 = 1 - q \ln (C/C_0) \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 / (C/C_0)^q \quad (4)$$

$$q = 2\tau_0 \sqrt{E/G} / \pi \sigma_0, \quad (5)$$

where E and G are effective moduli of elasticity and shear of composite;

σ_0 is the strength of samples without the man-made stress concentrator.

C_0 is the parameter characterizing the defects in samples without the man-made stress concentrator.

Fig.3. Strength of organic plastic versus crack c:
 1 - ring-shaped samples produced by winding one yarn, 2 - samples wound by a bundle consisting of 17 parallel yarns.

In fiber glass and organic fibre reinforced plastics defects of small-size model samples (strands or ring samples having a diameter of 150 mm and cross-section of 1.5m x 10mm)

are characterized by the value of C_0 that lies in the 40-150 μm range.

It is significant that in fiber glass and organic plastics the index of power (4) is much lower than 1/2 - the value typical of the Griffith criterion. This is responsible for the defects having a much smaller effect on the strength of fibrous composites than isotropic materials.

The values of the stress concentration coefficient in the fibers nearest to the cracks have been found [7] (See Fig.2):

$$K = 1 + q \ln (eN/\pi q), \quad (6)$$

where $N = C/h$ is the quantity of fractured fiber layers;

h is the thickness of one fiber layer with matrix (Fig. 2).

Eq.(6) reflects two major differences existing between the composites based on the plastic matrix and elastic matrix: 1) lower values of the stress concentration coefficient "K" and 2) dependence of "K" on the matrix properties. In composites with brittle matrices, if no delamination takes place in the crack tip, increasing length of crack causes "K" to grow proportionally to \sqrt{C} or \sqrt{N} [9].

According to [7], increase in the matrix yield point results in smaller ineffective length of fibres, on the one hand, and greater strength of the defectless material [10] and greater stress concentration in the vicinity of defects, on the other [6]. Competition of these antipodal factors causes the dependence of strength of real (defective) composite samples on the matrix yield point to reach their maximum (Fig.4).

The matrix yield point can be reduced by increasing the temperature of experiment T , decreasing the load rate or altering the matrix properties directly. The temperature dependence of the organic fibre reinforced plastic is shown in Fig.5.

Size and relative position of inclusions are important structural parameters that influence the plasticity of dis-

Fig.4. Glass fiber reinforced plastic strength versus matrix yield stress τ_0 : 1 - defectless material, $N=0$, $\beta=12$; 2 - $N=4$, $\beta=12$; 3 - $N=4$, $\beta=6$. β is the Weibull distribution coefficient characterizing the fiber strength distribution (higher strength dispersion corresponds to drop in β).

Fig.5. Strength of organic plastic (2,3) and yarn of organic fibers (1) versus temperature. 1 - yarn, 2 - microplastic samples, 3 - 150 mm dia ring-shaped samples.

persion-filled polymers. Filler particles catalyze the micro-deformation processes the development of which is largely dependent on local plastic properties of the matrix polymer and its deformation reinforceability. The effect of the size of aluminum hydroxyl inclusions (ALOH $d=1, 3, 8, 25, 55 \mu\text{m}$) on the deformation behaviour of the composite was studied using filled polyethylene of medium and superhigh molecular weight ($MW = 1.2 \times 10^4$ and 1.5×10^6 , respectively) [11]. Figure 4 shows failure deformations $\tilde{\delta}$ depending on the size of inclusions for the filled polyethylene of various MW. The filling extents at which this dependence is at its maximum are governed by the MW of the polymer and are shifted to the range of great values for the superhighmolecular polyethylene. It must be pointed out that fracture elongation is reduced both in large and small particles.

Fig.6. Elongation at rupture versus average diameter of inclusions: ● - average molecular weight polyethylene

($f_n = 14.4\%$);

□ - superhighmolecular weight polyethylene

($f_n = 32\%$).

Detailed structural analysis showed the material embrittlement not to be governed by agglomeration of filler particles or changing hypomolecular structure of the matrix polymer, when the particle sizes are altered. The size of hypomolecular formations does not seem to be a crucial factor either, as hardening of filled composites did not give rise to changes in the character of dependences shown in Fig.6. Interpretation of the dependences in question calls for a detailed analysis of the plastic failure process that takes place in high-density polyethylene.

Analysis of microdeformation processes carried out by the method of "in situ" tension of filled polyethylene samples of average molecular weight in the scanning electron microscope helped us to find that plastic fracture results from formation and plastic growth of micropores whose centres of formation are filler particles. The formation of pores begins on the surface of inclusions in the region of maximum tensile stresses. This surface fracture is caused by poor adhesion at the interface. Three stages of fracture exist: a) formation of pores; b) stabilization or growth of pores; c) fusion of micropores resulting in macroscopic crack.

Growth and fusion of micropores are controlled by geometric sizes of particles and their distribution in the composite. Large inclusions ($d=55\mu\text{m}$) initiate formation of large pores that avoid the stabilization stage and grow rapidly by fusing with the adjacent ones. This causes the material to failure.

A different situation arises in case of particles with $d = 8\mu\text{m}$. The pores formed are stabilized when their size is close to that of inclusions and plastic deformation takes place in adjacent regions of material. Stabilization of pores gives rise to yielding in a great volume of material. The particle size going still down ($d = 1\mu\text{m}$), a crase network is formed whose structure is common for homogeneous polymers. This is a characteristic feature of the microdeformation process if particle size is small. The crases consist of polymer fibrils (diameter $0.3 - 1\mu\text{m}$) with voids between them.

Plastic deformation is confined to fibrils and does not affect the bulk of polymer. Failure occurs at small macroscopic deformations as a result of plastic fracture inside the crazes. In all the cases analysed failure occurs at points with higher content of the filler.

Large failure deformation occur in filled polyethylene as a result of plastic deformation of big polymer volume. The analysis carried out showed the micropore stabilization stage to be of prime importance for increase in plasticity in the bulk of material. With the size of inclusions going down and their content by volume remaining constant, the absolute average thickness of the matrix between particles goes down as well. The energy dissipated as a result of yielding of thin matrix layers can be expected to decrease as the yielding region is decreased. This assumption is in close agreement with the data given in the first part of this work which show that the fracture energy decreases when polymer films get thinner. Behaviour of composites filled with $d = 1\mu\text{m}$ particles can be well used to illustrate the picture described below.

Hence, we should expect the ultimate deformations to increase together with the diameter of inclusions. This, indeed, takes place within a certain size range (Fig.4). Experiments in which samples were deformed in the scanning electron microscope showed, however, that the failure mechanism is changed when the particle diameter increases greatly. The pores formed on large-size particles are less stable. The fact that growing pores are grouped in the deformation instability zone is the reason for their fusion and failure of material.

With the use of superhighmolecular weight polyethylene structural homogeneity and deformation strengthening of polymer increase. As a result, the specific features of deformation behaviour mentioned above were seen at higher filling extents, i.e. when the gaps between particles were smaller.

Therefore, inclusions that are feebly bonded with the matrix polymer catalyze microdeformation processes in high-

density polymer, formation of a group of pores being an important element of these processes. Size and position of particles with respect to one another, absolute thickness of polymer interlayers, yielding and deformation hardening identify the region of stable and unstable growth of micropores in the stress field, thus providing for macroscopic plasticity of filled material.

SUMMARY

Structural defects of composite, great density fluctuations of the filler, in particular, are largely responsible for the limited growth of plastic deformation. It should be pointed out here that composite failure will be caused by the defect having the most unfavourable environment, rather than the greatest initial one. In the systems discussed such defects are especially dangerous at shock loading.

Unfortunately, at present, no adequate qualitative approach exists to describe the phenomena analysed above that are governed by the forms of plastic deformation together with microfracture of material. Our further efforts will be aimed at solving this problem.

Finally, it should be stressed that typical processes of polymeric composite failures are largely dependent on plastic deformation of polymer matrix. No qualitative and, quite often, quantitative failure theory can be created without taking into account the local plasticity of polymer.

REFERENCES

1. Stepanov V.A. In Problemy prochnosti i plastichnosti tverdykh tel (Problems of strength and plasticity of solids), (in Russian), Moscow, Nauka, 1973, pp.10-26.
2. Pakhomova L.K., Grineva N.S., Bavykin I.V. et al., Vysokomol.soed., 1981, v.XXIII(A), N2, 400-406.
3. Dagdale D. J.Mech.Phys.Solids, 1960, v.8, p.100.
4. McClintock F. In Fracture, ed. H.Liebowitz, Academic Press New York and London, 1972, v.3.
5. Olster E., Jones P. In Composite Materials, ed. L.J.Brautman and R.H.Crock, Academic Press, New York and London, 1974, v.1.
6. Berlin A.A., Grineva N.S., Aleksanyan G.G., Safonov G.P. Vysokomol.soed., 1986, v.XXYII (A), N 7, 1463-1487.
7. Bazhenov S.L., Berlin A.A. Dokl.Akad.Nauk SSSR, 1985,

- v.283, N6, p.1386.
8. Bazhenov S.L., Manevich L.I., Berlin A.A. et al. Dokl. Akad.Nauk SSSR, 1984, v.277, N4, 854-856.
 9. Hedgeheth J.M. Stress Concentrations in Filamentary Structures, NASA TN-D882, 1961.
 10. Gurland J., In Composite Materials, ed. L.J.Brautman and R.H.Crock, Academic Press, New York and London, 1974, v.5.
 11. Topolkaraev V.A., Tovmasyan Yu.M., Berlin A.A. et al., Dokl.Akad.Nauk SSSR, 1986, v.230, N6, 1418-1423.